

Annex to: Update of the risk assessment of mineral oil hydrocarbons in food.
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Annex C – Protocol for the human risk assessments related to the presence of mineral oil hydrocarbons (MOH) in food

The current protocol reports on the problem formulation and approach selected by the Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM Panel) to update the previous risk assessment of mineral oil hydrocarbons (MOH) in food. The protocol has been developed in accordance with the draft framework for protocol development for EFSA's scientific assessments (EFSA, 2020). This framework foresees that the extent of planning in the protocol (i.e. the degree of detail provided in the protocol for the methods that will be applied in the assessment) can be tailored to accommodate the characteristics of the mandate. Considering the timelines and the available resources, the CONTAM Panel decided to apply a low level of planning.

C.1. Problem formulation

Objectives of the risk assessment

The objective of the risk assessment is to assess the risk for adverse effects in humans associated with the dietary exposure to MOH in food.

The MOH to be considered are mineral oil saturated hydrocarbons (MOSH) and mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons (MOAH). MOH do not encompass the hydrocarbons naturally occurring in food, i.e. n-alkanes of predominantly odd-numbered carbons from C21 to C35, hydrocarbons of terpenic origin, such as squalene, and carotenoids. Polyolefin oligomeric saturated hydrocarbons (POSH), that may be present in food due to migration from plastic packaging (such as polyethylene or polypropylene), are not included in the term MOSH (EFSA, 2012, 2019a). However, considering the structural similarities with MOSH, studies on the toxicity of POSH and synthetic gas-to-liquid (GTL) oils will be taken into account in the assessment where relevant.

The CONTAM Panel Scientific Opinion on MOH in food in 2012 (EFSA, 2012) will be the starting point for the present update of the risk assessment. The range of hydrocarbons of relevance for the opinion are detailed in **Table C.1**.

Table C.1. MOH to be considered.

MOSH	<p>Information on saturated hydrocarbons with carbon number (Cn) ranging from >C10 to <C50 from the following studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies with single alkanes (both branched and unbranched). • Studies with single cycloalkanes (alkylated and non-alkylated, mono-, di- and higher ring systems) • Studies with mixtures of alkanes (both branched and unbranched) and/or cycloalkanes (alkylated and non-alkylated, mono-, di- and higher ring systems) <p>Studies with mixtures of MOSH and MOAH.</p>
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MOAH	<p>Information on aromatic hydrocarbons with Cn ranging from >C10 to <C50 from the following studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies with single aromatic hydrocarbons (mono-, di- and higher ring systems, including alkylated hydrocarbons and partially hydrogenated polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons). • Studies with mixtures of aromatic hydrocarbons (mono-, di- and higher ring systems, including alkylated hydrocarbons and partially hydrogenated polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons). • Studies with mixtures of MOSH and MOAH.
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Target populations

The target population of the human risk assessment is the European population, including specific vulnerable groups (fetus and breastfed infants) and groups with higher exposure due to dietary preferences.

MOH of concern and route of exposure

The risk assessment will focus on the chronic dietary exposure to MOH as in **Table C.1**.

Potential influence of hydrocarbons other than MOH on the outcome will be addressed in the uncertainty analysis.

Consideration will be given to potential non-dietary sources of exposure, e.g. dermal uptake, to indicate the relative importance of the diet to the overall MOH exposure.

Adverse effects and endpoints

The human risk assessment will address the adverse effects associated with the exposure to MOH as identified in the hazard identification step. On the basis of previous assessments, the evaluation of acute effects will be not considered, and the assessment will be restricted to chronic effects.

Identification of the risk assessment sub-questions

A series of sub-questions under each risk assessment pillar (i.e. hazard identification, hazard characterisation and exposure assessment) will be answered and combined for performing the risk assessment. The sub-question identified are reported in **Table C.2**.

Table C.2. Sub-questions to be answered for the risk assessment.

Risk assessment step	No	Sub-questions
Hazard identification	1	What adverse outcomes are caused by exposure to MOH ^(a) and similar hydrocarbons (e.g. POSH, GTL oils) in experimental animals?
Hazard identification	2	What adverse outcomes are associated with exposure to MOH and similar hydrocarbons (e.g. POSH, GTL oils) in humans?
Hazard identification	3	Are the different classes of MOH genotoxic?
Hazard characterisation	4	What is the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) of MOH in experimental animal species/strains and in humans?
Hazard characterisation	5	What is the difference in ADME of MOH between humans and experimental animals?
Hazard characterisation	6	What is the mode of action that can explain the observed adverse effects by MOH?
Hazard characterisation	7	What is the human relevance of adverse effect observed in experimental animals?
Hazard characterisation	8	What is the dose-response relationship between MOH and relevant endpoints in experimental animals and/or humans?
Exposure assessment	9	What are the analytical methods needed to make an adequate characterization and quantification of MOH in food?
Exposure assessment	10	What are the levels of MOH in food in Europe?
Exposure assessment	11	What is the effect of processing on the levels of MOH in food?
Exposure assessment	12	What are the consumption levels of foods contributing to MOH exposure among the European population?
Exposure assessment	13	What is the estimate of dietary exposure to MOH from the diet in the European population, including specific vulnerable groups and groups with high exposure?
Exposure assessment	14	What is the contribution of non-dietary exposure to the total exposure?
Exposure assessment	15	What are the concentrations of MOH measured in human tissues (e.g. blood, breast milk, adipose tissue, placenta) in the European population?
Exposure assessment	16	What is the relationship between the exposure levels and internal concentrations measured in human tissues?

ADME: absorption, distribution, metabolism and elimination.

(a): The MOH to be considered are mineral oil saturated hydrocarbons (MOSH) and mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons (MOAH) as specified in Table C.1.

Studies on both humans and experimental animals will be considered for the hazard identification and characterisation. The potential association between the target compound(s) and the endpoints of interest for the human risk assessment will be evaluated. It will include an assessment of the dose-response relationship for the derivation of a chronic Reference Point and an evaluation of possible uncertainties, for example those derived from consideration of the toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic properties of the target compounds and from considerations of the inter-species differences and intraspecies variability. As a next step, the human dietary exposure to the target compounds will be estimated. The final step will be the comparison of the exposure estimates to a health-based guidance value (HBGVs, e.g. a tolerable intake) or the calculation of margins of exposure (MOEs).

C.2. Method for answering the sub-questions

The sub-questions formulated in **Table C.2** will be answered by a comprehensive narrative approach. A literature search will be performed to identify primary research studies as well as reviews and meta-analysis relevant to the sub-questions formulated. In addition, the bibliography of the key full text papers will be checked for further potential relevant studies. This technique is known as snowballing. The expertise of the working group will be used in deciding whether to pursue these further to complement the evidence collection.

To inform the sub-questions related to the hazard identification and characterisation (**sub-questions 1 to 9**), all studies reporting effects in humans (i.e. epidemiological studies), and all *in vivo* studies in experimental animals that reported effects after exposure to the MOH will be considered. The eligibility criteria related to the report characteristic are listed in **Table C.3** (and apply to all sub-questions). The eligibility criteria related to study characteristics are listed in **Table C.4, C.5** and **C.6** for studies in humans, in experimental animals and toxicokinetic studies.

The details of the studies will be reported in tables and discussed in the corresponding section of the Opinion. The experimental animal studies will be reported by: (i) animal species, (ii) endpoint, (iii) target compound(s) tested and (iii) study duration. The human epidemiological studies will be reported by: (i) endpoint, (ii) target compound(s) analysed and (iii) study design.

The selection of the scientific studies for inclusion or exclusion will be done by the relevant domain experts from the CONTAM WG on MOH in food and CONTAM Panel. It will be based on consideration of the extent to which the study is relevant to the assessment, and on general study quality considerations (e.g. sufficient details on the methodology, performance and outcome of the study, on dosing, substance studied and route of administration and on statistical description of the results), irrespective of the results. Major limitations in the information used will be documented in the Scientific Opinion.

Table C.3. Eligibility criteria related to report characteristics (all sub-questions).

Language	In	English ^(a)
Time	In	From 2010
Publication type	In	Peer-reviewed primary research studies (i.e. studies generating new data), systematic reviews, reviews, meta-analyses, extended abstracts, PhD Theses
	Out	Editorials, letters to the editor, conference proceedings

(a): Studies in languages other than English might also be cited if considered relevant by the experts from the CONTAM WG on MOH in food or CONTAM Panel.

Table C.4. Eligibility criteria for the selection of human epidemiological studies.

Sub-questions 2 and 8		
Study design	In	Cross-sectional studies Cohort studies Case-control studies (retrospective and nested) Case series/Case reports Clinical trials
	Out	Animal studies <i>In vitro</i> studies
Study characteristics:	In	Any study duration Any number of subjects
	Out	/
Population	In	All populations groups, all ages, males and females Study location: all countries

	Out	/
Exposure/ intervention	In	All routes of exposure (dietary, dermal, inhalation, transplacental exposure). <u>Exposure:</u> - Studies in which levels of the MOH have been measured in human tissues - Studies in which the dietary exposure to the MOH has been estimated
	Out	/
Specific outcome of interest	In	All endpoints
	Out	/

Table C.5. Eligibility criteria for the selection of toxicological studies in experimental animals and *in vitro* studies.

Sub-question 1, 3, 6 and 8		
Study design	In	Experimental animal studies in mammals (e.g. rats, mice, monkeys, guinea pig, mini pigs, rabbit, hamster, dog, cat, mink) <i>In vitro</i> studies in relevant systems (primary mammalian cells, mammalian cell lines, subcellular interaction studies and bacterial cell lines used in genotoxicity studies as described in OECD Guidelines for the testing of chemicals)
	Out	Human studies, studies in non-relevant species.
Study characteristics:	In	Any study duration Any number of animals Any human culture cells/models
	Out	/
Population	In	Any age, males and females
	Out	/
Exposure/ intervention	In	<u>Route of administration:</u> Oral (feeding, gavage studies), <i>s.c.</i> , <i>i.p.</i> , <i>i.m.</i> <u>Compounds:</u> MOH as specified in Table A.1. and similar hydrocarbons (e.g. POSH, GTL oils) OR Estimated exposure validated <u>Number of doses:</u> single or repeated administration <u>Dose groups:</u> ≥ 1 dose groups + control group
	Out	Inhalation, dermal application Studies on hydrocarbons other than MOH as specified in Table A.1. and similar hydrocarbons
Specific outcome of interest	In	All endpoints
	Out	/

Table C.6. Eligibility criteria for the studies on toxicokinetics.

Sub-questions 4 and 5		
Study design / Test system	In	<i>In vivo</i> studies in humans <i>In vivo</i> studies in experimental animals <i>In vitro</i> studies in human culture cells/models <i>In vitro</i> studies in mammalian cells/models
	Out	/
Exposure/ intervention	In	<u>Route of administration:</u> Oral (feeding, gavage studies), <i>s.c.</i> , <i>i.p.</i> , <i>i.m.</i> MOH as specified in Table A.1.
	Out	/
Specific outcome of interest	In	Any outcome related to the absorption, distribution, metabolism and elimination of the target compounds

Information about previous risk assessments by international bodies, chemistry, analytical methods, current EU legislation, previously reported occurrence data in food and exposure assessments (including time trends), as reported in the literature, will be gathered and summarised in a narrative way (supported by tables, if relevant) based on expert knowledge and judgement.

The general principles of the risk assessment process for chemicals in food as described by WHO/IPCS (2009) will be applied, which include hazard identification and characterisation, exposure assessment and risk characterisation. In addition, the following EFSA guidance documents pertaining to risk assessment will be followed for the development of the risk assessment:

- Guidance of the Scientific Committee on transparency in the scientific aspects of risk assessments carried out by EFSA. Part 2: General principles (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2009),
- Management of left-censored data in dietary exposure assessment of chemical substances (EFSA, 2010a),
- Guidance of EFSA on the use of the EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database in exposure assessment (EFSA, 2011a),
- Overview of the procedures currently used at EFSA for the assessment of dietary exposure to different chemical substances (EFSA, 2011b),
- Scientific Opinion on genotoxicity testing strategies applicable to food and feed safety assessment (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2011)
- Guidance on selected default values to be used by the EFSA Scientific Committee, Scientific Panels and Units in the absence of actual measured data (EFSA SC, 2012a),
- Scientific Opinion on Risk Assessment terminology (EFSA SC, 2012b).
- Update: use of the benchmark dose approach in risk assessment (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2017a).
- Scientific Opinion on the guidance on the use of the weight of evidence approach in scientific assessments (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2017b).
- Guidance on the assessment of the biological relevance of data in scientific assessments (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2017c).
- Guidance on Uncertainty Analysis in Scientific Assessments (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2018).

Literature searches

The initial literature searches to inform the risk assessments on MOH were outsourced to an external provider. The literature search protocol agreed with the service provider is described in detail in (ref.). The searches will be regularly updated by the WG secretariat until a deadline to be agreed by the Working Group to allow the timely finalization of the opinion, as indicated, as described under A.6.

Integration of the lines of evidence for hazard identification and method to perform hazard characterisation

The final critical endpoints will be identified by integrating evidence from both human and experimental animal lines of evidence considering the respective level of confidence. A dose-response assessment will be performed on relevant adverse effects for the identification of chronic Reference Points, e.g. a benchmark doses (BMD) and its lower confidence limits (BMDL) or no-observed-adverse-effect levels (NOAEL) for a particular effect. The most relevant Reference Point will be considered for the possible derivation of an HBGV or to calculate the MOE.

Data on the toxicokinetics (ADME and toxicokinetic modelling) will support the extrapolation of results from experimental animal studies and human studies to the general population. This information will

also inform to determine which uncertainty factors related to inter-species difference and inter-individual variability need to be taken into account when establishing an HBGV or an MOE.

Information on mode of action will also support this step, as mode of action can describe the key events and their relationships required for the various adverse outcomes as a result of MOH exposure and inform the human relevance of effects observed in *in vivo* and *in vitro* experimental models.

C.3. Methods to address the exposure assessment sub-questions

For the risk assessment, all occurrence data received by the end of June 2021 and not used in previous scientific opinions will be considered

To address **sub-question 10** on the levels of MOH in food in European countries, a structured approach will be followed to collect and evaluate the evidence. Occurrence data are collected through the continuous annual call for data issued by EFSA requesting data on a list of prioritised chemical contaminants¹. National food authorities and also research institutions, academia, food business operators and other stakeholders are invited to submit data occurrence by the 1st of October of each year. The data submission to EFSA must follow the requirements of the EFSA Guidance on Standard Sample Description for Food and Feed (EFSA, 2010b); occurrence data will be managed following the EFSA standard operational procedures (SOPs) on 'Data collection and validation' and on 'Data analysis and reporting'. The available occurrence data on MOH in food will be extracted from the EFSA database by the EFSA Evidence Management Unit.

To guarantee an appropriate quality of the occurrence data used in the exposure assessment, the initial dataset will be evaluated before being used to estimate dietary exposure. This includes checks on the codification on FoodEx, the MOH levels reported, etc, but also on the analytical methods used (**sub-question 9-10**).

Regarding the consumption levels of relevant foods among the European population (**sub-question 12**), the EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database (Comprehensive Database) will be the source of the food consumption information. This database provides a compilation of existing national information on food consumption at individual level (last update on February 2020)².

The CONTAM Panel considered that only chronic dietary exposure to MOH is to be assessed for the general population. For this, food consumption and body weight data at the individual level will be accessed in the Comprehensive Database. Food occurrence data and consumption data will be linked at the least possible aggregated FoodEx level. In addition, the different food commodities will be grouped within each food category to better explain their contribution to the total dietary exposure to MOH. Exposure estimates will be calculated per dietary survey and age class. The mean and the high (95th percentile) chronic dietary exposures will be calculated by combining MOH mean occurrence values for food samples collected in different countries (pooled European occurrence data) with the average daily consumption for each food at individual level in each dietary survey.

To estimate the human dietary exposure and to identify the main food contributors to the exposure (**sub-question 13**), both occurrence and consumption data will be codified and classified according to the FoodEx classification system (EFSA, 2011c), simplifying their linkage when assessing the exposure to hazardous substances.

As indicated by the EFSA Working Group on Food Consumption and Exposure (EFSA, 2011b), dietary surveys with only one day per subject will not be considered as they are not adequate to assess repeated exposure. Similarly, subjects who participated only one day in the dietary studies, when the

¹ <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data/call/datex101217>

² <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/datexfoodcdb/datexfooddb>

protocol prescribed more reporting days per individual, will also be excluded for the chronic exposure assessment.

The estimates will be performed by the EFSA Evidence Management Unit. All analyses will be run using the SAS Statistical Software.

Sub-questions 11 and 14-15 will be addressed narratively by carrying out a literature search to identify reviews as well as other peer-reviewed single studies published in the open literature that will be screened and evaluated by relevant domain experts from the Working Group. **Sub-question 16** will be addressed by considering and combining the conclusions from the sub-questions 13, 14 and 15.

C.4. Methods to address the uncertainties in the risk assessment

The evaluation of the inherent uncertainties in the risk assessments on MOH will be performed based on the report on 'Characterizing and Communicating Uncertainty in Exposure Assessment' (WHO/IPCS, 2008) and the guidance on uncertainties of the EFSA Scientific Committee (EFSA Scientific Committee, 2018) and the guidance on communication of uncertainty in scientific assessments (EFSA, 2019b). Uncertainties will be assessed qualitatively and quantitatively as appropriate. The uncertainties will be considered with reference to the Risk Assessment Roadmap and the tables of uncertainties for hazard identification and characterisation and exposure commonly found in CONTAM opinions.

Recommendations will be included in the Scientific Opinion for the generation of additional data that could decrease the impact of the identified uncertainties on the conclusions of the risk assessment.

C.5. Approach for reaching risks characterisation conclusions

The general principles of the risk characterisation for chemicals in food as described by WHO/IPCS (2009) will be applied as well as the different EFSA guidance documents relevant to this step of the risk assessment (see **Section A.1** above).

C.6. Plans for updating the literature searches and dealing with newly available evidence

The literature searches performed will be repeated approximately 2 months before the planned date of endorsement for public consultation of the Opinion. The scientific papers retrieved by these additional searches will be screened for relevance by the members of the Working Group and EFSA staff and included in the draft Opinions as appropriate by the Working Group experts.

C.7. Public consultation

The Opinion will be subject to a public consultation to receive input from interested parties on a draft Opinion. The comments will be considered for finalisation of the Opinion.

C.8. History of the amendments to the protocol

Amended on 3 August 2021.

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